

Globalization, Diaspora & the Cultural Landscape

- The case of Bharatanatyam in the Diaspora

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'Civilized man lives really in three worlds: the world of instant, the world of memory, and the world of art. To deprive him of the latter would be to change, to an almost inconceivable degree, the whole character of living. After it was gone, memory itself could be taken away without involving a second impoverishment which is more disastrous than that which has resulted when he had been left with nothing except memory to preserve him from complete solution in the flux of phenomena'.

Joseph Wood Krutch (1962:78)

Human society, like a living organism, has several systemic needs for its survival. Each of these needs results in creation of certain institutions such as nutrition, family, kinship, education system, religion, etc. Malinowski (1884-1942), a famous Anthropologist, observed that all human culture could eventually be reduced to the satisfaction of basic needs. Rituals, kinship patterns, economic exchanges are the outcome of these needs. Cultural and symbolic needs are responded by religion, music and performing arts, etc. Cultural needs are vital not only for the maintenance of the social order but also for the social integration as a whole. Performing arts, music, literature, etc. fulfill the cultural needs of the human being and thus socializes human beings to live in a particular society.

Each community or society 'establishes a mode of existence, a distinct way of understanding itself, its activity, its history and the world it inhabits, specific to it and all-embracing in its compass' (Shanker, R, 1998). This is what we call culture of a community or society, which includes both material and non-material resources such as Art, Music, Dance, Sculpture, etc. Therefore, Culture becomes a total social heritage acquired by man as a member of the Society. It is shared and has distinctive forms (patterns) and thus shapes human behaviour.

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Dancing is one of the most important cultural practices in many societies. Dancing is the first art and the earliest impulse that takes an outward embodiment in human being (Urlin: 2002). Movement, dance, music, and ritual can usefully be treated as modes of human communication on a continuum from the nonverbal to the verbal. All four modes can express ideas that bring together spheres of human activity: social, political, economic, religious and so on (Blacking, J, 1985:64-65). The social role of dance can be perceived as transmission and sentiment, cultural practices and maintenance of identity. Cultural practices such as dance travel with human being as they migrate from one place to another. The new migratory community often nourishes their culture in the alien soil. This holds true especially in the case of Diaspora population.

Diaspora is a term often used today to describe practically any population that is considered "deterritorialised" or "transnational"- that is, which has originated in a land other than in which it currently resides, and whose social, economic and political networks cross the borders of nation-states or, indeed, span the globe (Vertovec, Steven: 1997:277). Indian Diaspora has her deep roots in the ancestral land and maintains extensive cultural links. Indian way of life and culture is no longer just confined to its geographical boundaries; rather it has its presence wherever Indians have emigrated along with their 'socio-cultural baggage'. This article tries to highlight some of the important aspects of Indian culture in the Indian Diaspora. Taking the case of Bharatanatyam, a popular classical dance form in the Indian diaspora, this article deals with the following:

- 1 How Bharatanatyam plays an important role in fulfilling the cultural needs and asserting identity of Indian Diaspora community.
- 2 Brief history of Bharatanatyam in India and its Diaspora (with reference to both Colonial and Post-Colonial Diaspora/New Diaspora).
- 3 Bharatanatyam beyond Diaspora - Global Harmony, Cultural Diplomacy, and
- 4 Cultural interaction in the international arena and its impact on Bharatanatyam.

These four dimensions intersect one another in significant ways. An attempt has been made in the article to highlight these dimensions under different sections.

I. Globalization, Diaspora and Indian Cultural Landscape

Since time immemorial, the questing ambition has moved man from region to region, who crossed rivers and mountains to reach distant lands. History has yet

to reveal a period in which human migrations and cultural interaction did not take place. (Asthana, Shashi, 1985:211)

Cultural transaction between the social groups in the past was generally restricted—firstly, due to geographical and ecological constraints and lack of communication channels (satellite, Internet, etc.) and secondly, because of active resistance to interaction with others. Diaspora, which is both a product and process of globalization, brought about a sea change in cultural transaction both in the sending and the receiving countries in the late twentieth century. With emigration, human beings invariably carry with them a socio-cultural baggage which consists of, among other things, social identity, a set of religious beliefs and practices, norms and values governing family and kinship, food habits, dress and language. They settle in the host society as immigrants and strive to maintain their relations with the kith and kin at the place of origin. These immigrants become permanent features of the host society once they acquire citizenship and their hopes for returning to their 'motherland' gradually recede. But, the migrants are not cut off from the land of their origin as globalization has caused new opportunities and forms in which traditional culture can thrive. Here culture becomes a connecting device that links together nations and people in different parts of the world and globalization speeds up the natural process of cultural interaction, blends them together and helps in forming fresh cultures.

Globalization, defined as a proliferation of cross-border flows and transnational networks, has changed the context for migration. New technologies of communication and transport allow frequent and multi-directional flows of people, ideas and cultural symbols (Castles, S, 2002:1143). Indian emigration has been taking place for centuries but never before in history has India witnessed such massive movement of people to other parts of the world as in the 19th and 20th centuries. Today there are over 20 million People of Indian Origin (PIOs) including Non-resident Indians (NRIs) who still retain their passports, settled in about 70 countries (Ministry of External Affairs: 2001). Demographically, overseas Indians form the third largest diaspora, next only to British and Chinese. People of Indian Origin constitute more than 40 percent of the population in Fiji, Mauritius, Trinidad and Tobago, Guyana and Surinam. They are smaller minorities in Malaysia, South Africa, Sri Lanka, Uganda, UK, USA and Canada.

Since India's independence in 1947, overseas Indians have been frequent visitors to their places of origin to maintain their linkages or to seek their roots. People of Indian Origin (PIO) have continued to nurture close socio-cultural relationship with their motherland. These relationships are primarily cultural in

nature, in the spheres of religion, language and region, films, music and performing arts. The focal point in the construction of diaspora identity is home, either imaginary or real. Through the network of family, kin, friends, colleagues and various other 'significant others', immigrant people relate home. This recreated home 'outside homeland' is a place, which make immigrant people remain intimate even in moments of intense alienation from it. Thus, Culture plays a vital role in sustaining the Diaspora's identity.

II Cultural Identity: Bharatanatyam in Indian Diaspora

As an essential aspect or ingredient, dance helps identify the culture, taste and attitude of the people. In a large multi-lingual country like India, culture would not represent a single unified set of values or ideas but would indeed be multi-dimensional in character depending on the cross fertilization of ideas, values and systems obtained from different parts of the country (Vaidyanathan, S. 1984:1). Bharatanatyam, which has links with principles and techniques of dance systematized 2000 years ago in Bharata's *Natyasastra* - the oldest treatise on dance, reflects the deep philosophical and religious moods of Indian people.

With the birth of the industrial age and with the coming of the modern age, there was a growth of leisure class and dance became a form of entertainment to fill empty hours. Bharatanatyam became one of the popular forms of performing art in India though it had several ups and downs along its history of development. This popularity can be attributed to two main reasons:

- 1 Early revival.
- 2 Increasing fancy among the middle class.

Bharatanatyam is one of the dance forms, which had its revival earlier than most other classical Indian dance forms. This revival or resurrection, as it may be called, was a part of the nationalist awakening that led to an upsurge in the feeling of Indianness among the general public. Rukmini Devi Arundale, E. Krishna Iyer and many others who spearheaded this revivalist movement during the 1930's, gave a fresh impetus to Bharatanatyam that was until then performed by the Devadasis and was associated with ill repute. When such a dance form which was till then looked down upon, was brought to the stage and also performed by the revivalists who were mainly from the upper class, it caught the fancy of many sections of the society - mainly the middle class who almost formed the majority of the population. Thus with increasing middle class, the dance form also gained newer spaces of enormous acceptance gradually among the general community.

Today, Bharatanatyam is very popular amongst all classical dance forms. It is considered to be the most ancient and the richest in content and expression and so can be taken to be the truest representative of the nation's cultural tradition, with a history as old as civilization itself.

Today, human society encounters three tendencies operating concurrently (Mukherjee, R., 1991: 62):

(1) Homogenization of culture in the global scale, along with the globalization of economy and polity, (2) Assertion of homogenized culture in different configurations of human society, usually in respective nation-states, and (3) Demand of ethnic groups, at discerning levels of their power potential within a nation state, for the recognition of 'minority' culture.

Maintaining minority culture is a more visible development all across the globe. Modern societies are increasingly confronted with minority groups demanding recognition of their identity, and accommodation of their cultural difference.

Kymlicka's observation holds true in the context of immigrant and diaspora community. He says 'they typically wish to integrate into the larger society, and to be accepted as full members of it. While they often seek greater recognition of their ethnic identity, their aim is not to become a separate and self-governing nation alongside the larger society, but to modify the institutions and laws of the mainstream society to make them more accommodating of the cultural difference (Kymlicka, W, 2001: 213).

Human beings carry both the baggage and the heritage from the collective society, family, organization, and relationship that are part of the process of growth (Parikh, I & et.al. 2002: 6). This is important for the formation of Diaspora community. The socio-economic, political and cultural practices of the group help them to construct the ethnic identity and creating the home. Members of the Indian diaspora are deeply conscious of their rich cultural heritage. They are aware that they are the inheritors of the traditions of one of the world's oldest continuous civilization. Being part of such a rich legacy, they are naturally keen to maintain their cultural identity (ICWA, 2001: 403). Today, Indian culture has been spreading to almost all parts of the world and Indian diaspora has been playing an important role in promoting Indian culture abroad. Thus dance, which upholds their cultural values, becomes a part of the socio-cultural baggage that the Indians carry with them.

Bharatanatyam became for the diaspora, a means of retaining connections with one's Indian ness while functioning far from home, and also an expression reinforcing and asserting one's separate ethnic identity, while remaining part of a larger multi-cultural society (Venkataraman, L., 2001:5). Thus it also became an effective medium to communicate Indian culture to the Indian diaspora people. In the 1980s and 1990s Bharatanatyam circulated through ever-more global trajectories (O'shea, J. 2003:176). The dance form operates, as Arjun Appadurai (1996) observes, intentional cultural reproduction for Non Resident Indians in places as divergent as Los Angeles, Singapore, and Manchester.

The Colonial Diaspora

The countries to which emigrants from India travelled as indentured and plantation labourers under colonial rule included mainly the former British, French and Dutch colonies. The popularity of Bharatanatyam in the colonial diaspora can be attributed to three important developments:

1. Growing number of middle-class population: People of Indian origin have been facing number of challenges since colonial time. These challenges made them to work hard and survive in the host society. Gradually with the hard work and dedication they could prosper economically. This resulted in not only providing proper education to their children but also to train them in many other fields to face the future challenge in the host countries, politically, educationally, culturally and economically. Indian dance led by Bharatanatyam became a cultural tool by which the middle class diasporic community asserted its presence and roots to heritage.
2. Development of communication, satellite and transportation: This is one of the most important developments after World War II. The communication revolution brought people of the world closer. It also served the community by facilitating interaction with the ancestor's land (India) virtually. Thus cultural exchange became easier between people across the world. Today, Indian Television channels such as Zee T.V., Sun T.V, Vijay T.V and many other regional and national channels reach the Diaspora community. Bharatanatyam as a dance form became popular among the diaspora community mainly through Indian movies. Faster and better modes of communication like telephone and Internet have also helped to facilitate easy interaction between many artists and organizations across the world.
3. Role of Cultural Associations and individual artists: Promoting Indian culture abroad is one of the missions of the government of India. At present India has

cultural centers in the following cities: Port Louis (Mauritius), Paramaribo (Suriname), Georgetown (Guyana), Port of Spain (Trinidad and Tobago), Colombo (Sri Lanka), London (UK), Jakarta (Indonesia), Durban and Johannesburg (South Africa), Almaty (Kazakhstan), Tashkent (Uzbekistan), Cairo (Egypt) and Berlin (Germany). In addition to this, centres like Nehru Centre and Bharatiya Vidya Bhavan, promote Indian culture abroad. Indian artists, especially in classical music and dance, are frequently invited by Indian diaspora. There are also quite a large number of community organizations, religious organizations and temples that popularize Bharatanatyam and other forms of classical dances in their respective regions.

Though the Indian population is less in Singapore, Malaysia, Trinidad and Tobago, Guyana and Mauritius, one can find quite a significant number of artists there. Indian Government started several joint ventures to promote Indian culture in these countries. The Mahatma Gandhi Institute (MGI) was set up in 1970 as a joint venture between the government of India and the government of Mauritius. It serves as a centre for the study of Indian culture and traditions and for the promotion of education and culture in general. The Institute offers course on Indian classical dance. Children at secondary school level (12- 18 years old) onwards participate in these dance courses¹. There are Indian troupes visiting these countries facilitated by ICCR.

Today, Bharatanatyam is more than an art form for the diaspora community. To quote Joan L. Erdman, it is 'a way of thinking, of moving, of being' (Venkataraman,L, 2001:5). Unlike Western audiences, Indian audiences have a strong personal identification with the stories and characterization of epics and myths. Thus, Bharatanatyam serves as timeless reminder of an individual's social and ethnic identity (IED, 1998:160). Today, Bharatanatyam receives and fulfils the taste of contemporary audience in India and abroad too by imbibing contemporary themes.

The Post-Colonial / New Diaspora

The popularity of Bharatanatyam among the diaspora community in USA and Europe can be attributed to the socio-economic conditions of Indians living there. There have been several changes in the world economy, politics and culture since World War II. USA emerged as the most powerful economy in the world. It needed a vast number of professional labours to keep its economy reviving. In addition to this, USA also emerged as one of the most favoured destinations for the intellectuals and professionals to make a good fortune. UK and many other European countries

have also attracted many professionals and intellectuals from developing countries. This resulted in migration of significant number of professionals from India, China and other third world and developing countries to USA, Europe, Australia and Japan. These immigrants become a permanent feature of the host society once they acquire the citizenship and their hopes for returning to their 'motherland' gradually recede. More importantly, the migrants are not inevitably irrevocably cut off completely from the land of their origin. They have not only retained Indian culture and tradition but also revived it in many ways.

The growing popularity of Bharatanatyam in America is partly attributed to the economic success of the Indians (Venkataraman, L. 2001:5) and partly because of its inherent strength, which is rooted in tradition. Bharatanatyam's close adherence to Indian tradition helps the spectators identify themselves with their culture as it is. Obviously, the homeless community derives much needed solace from this traditionally rich form of art.

Bharatanatyam has official support in Canada. The Canadian government recently has decided to expand its national Arts Training Contribution Programme to include traditions other than European. Kala Bharati, which is one of the beneficiaries of this programme has organised Bharatanatyam teacher training programme under the guidance of Dr. Mamata Niyogi Nakra (Purvadhanashree. 2003:2). Lata Pada, a Canada based danseuse, who has made Bharatanatyam popular through her cross-cultural and multimedia productions- 'Revealed by fire' being her latest one, says that she has about 150 students from different ethnic backgrounds. She observes that 'there is a huge wave of Indian culture in Canada, from Indian cuisine, to fashion to Bollywood films, music and classical dance' (Kapur, S. 2003).

Today, Indians in USA, UK and other European countries are quite economically prosperous. Their occupation ranges from professions such as Medicine, Law, Engineering, Business, and Software etc. to semi-skilled jobs. They form a middle class and higher middle class category in the country and can afford to spare time for cultural and community activities. Leela Venkataraman observes, 'It was not long before Bharatanatyam dancers as wives of Doctors

Lata Pada with her students in her latest production - 'Revealed by Fire'

and Engineers serving abroad, cautiously ventured into starting Bharatanatyam teaching classes in basements' (2001:5).

The identity of Indian-American Bharatanatyam dance student is in constant negotiation: thick with cultural memory, social commentary and opposing dimensions spawned from the westernized school and media on one hand and Bharatanatyam classes on the other. Bharatanatyam ultimately becomes a cultural defense, unraveling nostalgia in a search for roots, healing displacement while simultaneously creating new meanings, inferences and chasms (Anu Ganpati, a-34).

Some of the dancers who have popularized Bharatanatyam and have created a niche for themselves in USA, UK, Australia, Canada, France, Singapore and a lot of other countries include artists like Malathi Iyengar, Nirupama Vaidhyathanar, Sreelatha Suresh, Mythili kumar, Hema and Krithika Rajagopalan, Rathna Kumar, Menaka Thakkar, Lata Pada, Vidhya Jagdish, Deepa Ganesh, Nirmala Sheshadri and Anandavalli to mention a few. It is usually found that they are mainly concentrated in areas where the immigrant Indian population is high.

In a multi-ethnic society with a substantial presence of later-day immigrants, it is a challenge to keep Bharatanatyam alive with its distinct Identity. It is significant that in as much as African, European and Asian arts have from time to time, been integrated into the melting pot which is America, Bharatanatyam has not become just an amorphous art of this cocktail of cultural strains. (Venkataraman, Leela. 2001:43)

III. Development and Change

Dance involves symbols and gestures, which are very indexical in their meaning. Only the spectators who have a grounding knowledge of Indian philosophy can understand it properly. Thus there is a need to bring some kinds of innovation to make it understandable to the new spectators.

The observation of Kapila Vatsyayan in the context of multicultural society holds true. 'The aesthetic enjoyment of the classical Indian dance is considerably hampered today by the wide gap between the dancer and the spectator. Even the accomplished dancer, in spite of his/her mastery of the classical technique, may sometimes only be partially initiated in the essential qualities of the dance form and its aesthetic significance. But, in the case of the audience, only the exceptional spectator is acquainted with the language of symbols through which the artist achieves the transformation into the realm of art. The majority are somewhat

baffled by a presentation which is obviously contextual and allusive but which derives from traditions to which they have no ready access' (Vatsyayan, Kapila.1968:2).

Bharatanatyam is usually referred to as an ethnic dance of India in the West. Sudha seetharaman of Trilok fusion says, "in the U.S., Bharatanatyam is really not given the status of a classical dance as the west would to the ballet. Actually Ballet does not need half the training that an Indian classical dance would. Yet, there, our dance is often associated with the folk dances of Africa and is referred to as an ethnic dance of India. We get tired of telling the organizers that Bharatanatyam has a history of its own, that it owes its origin to a standardized, ancient treatise called *Natyashastra*, adheres to the stringent norms laid within this and requires rigorous training" (Kumar, Rane: 2003).

From being esoteric, Bharatanatyam has begun to find new grounds with a lot more innovative ventures beginning to be undertaken. This started with Uday Shankar (father of modern dance in India) in the early 1920's. With him, the ideas of east and west began to be used to promote Indian dance abroad. Innovative works like "Jazz-Natyam", which is a fusion of Bharatanatyam and Jazz music by Sudha Seetharaman in the U.S., Flamenco-Natyam which is a fusion of Bharatanatyam and Flamenco of Spain by Rajika Puri and a lot other contemporary works by dancers like Sujatha Srinivasan in Ohio, Jyothi Raghavan in Massachusetts, Raghunath Manet in France, Jayanthi Raman in Portland and Lata Pada in Canada, are helping a lot in taking Bharatanatyam to the world audience and in creating a niche for the form and its exponents in the International dance arena. More over, conferences like the one on dance in Indian Diaspora held in North America in Sep-2001 not only provides a ground for examining the present state of Bharatanatyam but also explores its future fate in the Diaspora.

Rajika Puri and La Conja in
Flamenco Natyam

Further more, programs like 'studie's on international factors affecting dance in Asian diaspora', conducted by the Faculty of Dance at University of California riverside and those offered by Center for Performing Arts in India, a component of University of Pittsburgh, and the National University of Singapore's Indian dance unit, and other such ones, would not only enhance the knowledge on different

aspects of dance in diaspora, but also help understanding the challenges encountered by the Diaspora dancers.

Looking at the presence and growth of Bharatanatyam in Diaspora, its different stages of development can be illustrated as follows:

Growth of Bharatanatyam in the Diaspora/ Multicultural set up

The Traditional Bharatanatyam, taken as a part of socio-cultural baggage by the migrant, becomes an 'Ethnic dance form' when practiced in the Diaspora. As it is on the margin of two cultures and two societies, which are not fused together, it becomes a 'Marginal dance form' with the tag "Indian ethnic dance". Here, as the migrant and the local cultural traits flourish side by side, one can find two types of totally different cultures at one place and at one time where a 'contact situation' develops (Asthana, S, 1985:211).

The phenomenon of marginality does not last for long if in the new society, cultural assimilation happens on a faster pace. If not, the dance form gradually develops with some contemporary inputs pertaining to its own culture and becomes a form with a separate identity. In the process of its development, it may leave behind some traditional elements and take up new ideas to promote the popularity of the dance and enrich its repertoire. But all this happens without shifting from the particular idiom called Bharatanatyam.

When it succeeds in maintaining and growing with a separate identity, 'Bharatanatyam' may break off from the tag "Indian ethnic dance" and go on to be accepted as an international dance form.

On the other hand if from the contact situation, there begins an inter-flow of ideas from different marginal cultures, the resultant will be a fused form of Bharatanatyam which would have elements from other cultures welded to its own. The examples can be found in Jazz Natyam and Flamenco Natyam done by Sudha Seetharaman and Rajika Puri respectively of the USA and other such collaborations. This fused form gradually might then become a 'Hybrid', which is an absolute blending together of all that is good and true in either. Here Bharatanatyam may or may not retain its original name. An example of the hybrid form can be found in works of artists like Shobana Jeyasingh of UK, Uttara Coorlawala of New York and Lata Pada of Canada.

Lata Pada with Trinidadian dancer - choreographer Ronald

Like many other arts in India, Bharatanatyam is also undergoing several changes. As veteran music director and singer Ravindra Jain observes 'the root of the Indian music were deep and it could not be shaken by the western form of music...Indian music is perennial and everlasting'. His views holds true in case of other art like Bharatanatyam, which is deep rooted in the Indian civilization. His observations are certainly not an ethnocentric one. Given the long tradition of Indian art and culture, any western observer can also view the same. He however cautions that 'learning western music or patronising it was not bad, but it should not be done at the cost of our musical heritage'.

Organizational Effort

Cultural organizations like ICCR of Government of India and several Indian community cultural organizations in respective countries are promoting Indian art and music.

SPICMACAY (Society for the Promotion of Indian Classical Music and Culture amongst Youth), founded in India in 1977, promotes awareness of Indian cultural

traditions amongst the younger generation of Indians. It has its presence in several parts of the world and organizes classical music and dance concerts, lecture demonstrations, workshops and other related activities in Schools and Universities.

The People of Indian Origin Card (PIO Card) launched by the Ministry of Home Affairs in March 1999 facilitates to promote the emotional bonds of Indians abroad with their motherland. This will certainly help in promoting cultural ties not only between Indian and its diaspora, but also in the spreading of Indian culture in their respective host countries at a faster rate.

Some of the recommendations made in the Report of the High Level Committee on Indian diaspora (ICWA, 2001:411-413) which include the following, would also help in sustaining and building a strong cultural connection with the Indian Diaspora.

1. Opening admissions to cultural institutions.
2. Youth travel programmes in which this generation of the new Indian diaspora can travel to India and learn about her culture and the challenge she faces.
3. Multi-disciplinary scholarships for the diaspora would facilitate Indian Diaspora students to carry out research in their fields of specialization in India.
4. Recognition of the achievements of the Diaspora by the Indian government.
5. Revival of the Festivals of India with focus on the Indian diaspora and its substantial involvement.

The first and the second can include programmes like 'Study India Programme'(SIP), currently being offered for foreign students by the University of Hyderabad. There have been initiatives by Institutes such as Mahatma Gandhi Institute, Mauritius and University of Hyderabad for an exchange programme in the field of art and culture. In these programmes, the diaspora can come into contact and learn from the traditional gurus and artists of Bharatanatyam. University level multi-disciplinary studies mainly on the research-front would not only bring in a lot more scope for participation in cross-cultural studies, but also throw open an entirely new dimension in creating better and much more innovative ventures for dance research.

Apart from presenting performances in the diaspora, Bharatanatyam dancers in the diaspora are slowly finding place even in the popular December festival

season in Chennai. Some private organisations like 'Hamsadhwani' in Chennai have started providing platforms solely for the NRIs to exhibit their talents in dance and music.

There are databases like the one provided by Nartaki.com, which gives information on dancers in Indian Diaspora and institutions. All these efforts can help in creating wide-ranging networks for artists in popularizing the dance form.

IV. Bharatanatyam beyond Diaspora: Global harmony and Cultural diplomacy

In recent times, there has been more concern for global harmony and development incorporating cultural values and gender justice. There is also the question of stemming the rising tide of racial, ethnic and communal conflicts; coping with the threat to cultural distinctions and identity (Sharma, S.L. 2002: 80).

Mulk Raj Anand, a well-known literary figure, is of the opinion that 'Under the conditions of co-existence, India hopes for exchange of cultures in order to promote understanding between nations' (1963:139). 'Culture' is expected to play a role in shaping international relations (Sahai, 2003:33). According to Sahai, 'its role has been viewed differently at different times in different societies. In the olden times, culture followed trade in some cases, like Silk Route, while in other cases, trade followed culture, like spread of Buddhism in South East Asia'. It is the 'cultural strength of a country that gives it cohesiveness, endurance and memory to carry the country forward as a civilization in the world' (Singh, B.P, 1998: 74).

Massive migration of people from one country to another makes many societies multicultural; and so there arises a need for cultural understanding between one another's culture to maintain order in the particular society. Diaspora group can also play an important role for promoting cultural understanding.

Today, the Indian diplomacy is more aware of the importance of culture as 'soft power' in global politics and international relations. The influence of great powers is generally measured in indices of "hard power" such as military capability. In contrast, soft power is the ability to influence other societies through real but intangible elements as culture (Mohan,R.,2003:11). The main weapon of US diplomacy has been Hollywood movies, Coke and McDonald's, which spread American values all over the world. Alongside war with Iraq, America has been influencing the mind of people of Iraq with Hollywood movies and other media (Times of India,2003:11). Similar are the cases of Russia and China. The fact is

'strength of culture is more than military might and enduring'.

'Indian Diaspora is the biggest instrument of our soft power' as emphasized by the Indian external affairs minister Mr. Yashwant Sinha (Mohan, R, 2003: 11). Indian Diaspora can play the role of unofficial cultural ambassador in many of the countries of their settlement.

Indian Council of Cultural Relations (ICCR), which has the primary responsibility for promoting India's cultural relations with foreign countries, has used three important instrumentalities -Chairs of Indian Studies, Cultural Centers and Festivals of India- in promoting cultural interests in the broader context. These also include undertaking activities connected with promotion of Indian art, music and dance. (Sahai, 2003:35)

The peaceful co-existence and positive contribution to the settlement society by Indians is evident. The survey of the Diaspora in various countries clearly demonstrates that Indians have seldom sought conflict with their fellow citizens of the countries of their residence. What does one attribute this to? The answer lies in the deep-rooted commitment to the cultural and civilizational ethos of India (ICWA, 2001: 403).

Bharatanatyam, which is deeply rooted in Indian philosophy, can make immense contribution towards the understanding of Indian civilization by people of different societies. Music, dance and other forms of arts reflect Indian culture in a big way. Bharatanatyam, which incorporates several aspects of Indian traditions, mythology and Indian social values, can thus help the foreign audience understand the socio-psychological life of the people in a positive way.

Conclusion

Some sociological observation might be of help to understand the rapidly changing atmosphere through which Bharatanatyam as an art form seems to be moving today. Like many other Indian traditional art, Bharatanatyam is in a challenging situation both inside and outside India. In India, it has had several ups and downs throughout its long history. Often, it disappeared from public consciousness when Devadasi system was associated with it and was looked down upon. However, it has regained its popularity throughout India in recent times, especially amongst the middle class population. The future prospect of Bharatanatyam in the Diaspora depends upon the socio-economic and political condition of the settlement society and the position that the Indian Diaspora has in that society. It is difficult to have a healthy environment for preservation of the

cultural forms such as Bharatanatyam in countries where racism is practiced. Some of the countries are averse to a certain degree towards multicultural society and in some countries racism has been practiced covertly. For example Germany and some African countries and to some extent Malaysia have been quite averse towards diversity of culture.

The interaction with the outside world opens a community to learn and acquire other culture. In the context of Indian diaspora in Britain, Tessa Jowell, the British Minister for Culture, Media and Sports, observes, 'globalization speeds up the natural process by which cultures meld together and form fresh cultures. Britain, enriched by the contributions of British Indians, is living proof of this cultural give-and-take' (Jowell, T., 2003:16). This resulted in adding complexity to the original culture. This happened in the case of Bharatanatyam too. As noted dance critic Dr. Sunil Kothari observes, 'with the unprecedented global popularity of a form like Bharatanatyam today, the dance scene is overcrowded not only within India but also abroad. This has led to subtle shifts in meanings and context and a whole new sociology of the form is needed to grasp the complexity of its specificities. The diaspora of Indians who have settled abroad practicing, performing and teaching classical dance forms have added to the complexity (1999).

On the technological front and the popular taste of the global audience, certain changes have occurred in Bharatanatyam. Since late 1960s, an increasing number of international dance troupes have been performing throughout the world. The performers and their managers, promoters and producers are not oblivious to the professional hallmarks of dance or to the technological wonders of the world through which they travel. Technology and the global audience have unquestionably accelerated the rate of change (IED, 1998:163).

Now there are more urban-bred dancers, educated in a system based largely on Western concepts of education, living in a modern technological society. The dance-world is influenced by cinema, with its images of success, by tours, by elaborately staged presentations and theatrical effects,

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and now by growing television exposure. All these factors orient the choices confronting the dancer or the teacher-choreographer who attempts to create within the scope of Indian dance and music; but with an awareness of contemporary developments (IED, 1998: 461).

There have been challenges to Bharatanatyam in the Diaspora. Kothari (1999) observes, 'the second generation of the NRIs whose acolytes are studying classical dance forms often give up after a few years. This is bound to happen. For the young brought up in an alien culture cannot but remain aloof and not mix with their peer group'. 'To make a career as a dancer in a multicultural society is not easy. Competition is severe and unless there is a sound support system, it is tough to follow a course, which is not "a paying one". Though the Arts Councils in the respective countries offer grants and financial award to artists who have settled there, the competition continues to grab the money, position and opportunities to perform. In the final analysis those who have the grit and merit succeed or survive over a long period. Often the dancers coming into contact with the other culture branch off into areas of experimentation, fusion and innovation' (Kothari, S : 1999).

Simultaneously, changes are taking place, making the dance form an aesthetic expression of their current society and lives. Each century, each era and each millennium provides a context to enrich the meaning of their lives and redesign the nature of relationships amongst themselves and other collectivities. Bharatanatyam as a dance form has addressed these issues through the work of artists and made the art more contemporary.

To be optimistic about the prospect of Bharatanatyam, an observation makes sense. 'Two factors, which had enormous influence on dance in India and abroad, are (1) Mass Media: particularly motion picture industry and (2) Mass Audience that the media have brought to dance. Motion picture employed several classical dancers including Bharatanatyam artists in its initial stage and made the art form popular among the mass audiences. Prior to this, the art was only for certain class of audiences. The future of Indian dance form, including Bharatanatyam seems assured' (IED: 1998: 168).

In the last century, technology, especially the communication revolution, changed the way we lived and changed the way we worked. Two world wars, the creation and the use of atom bombs, partition, and the proxy cold war, the resultant destruction, and human trauma created the context for the emergence of need for newer forms of expression and inner enrichment. Understanding each other's

culture helps to have a better relationship and world peace. Bharatanatyam, which encompasses the Indian philosophy, has much to offer to the people of Indian origin in particular and to the world in general.

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